

A Geographical Study of Food Consumption Pattern and Calorie Intake among the Tribal People of Dindori District (M.P.), India

Paper Id : 19930 Submission Date : 2025-01-01 Acceptance Date : 2025-01-20 Publication Date : 2025-01-25
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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.15202635

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Abstract

The food consumption pattern among the tribal people of the district Dindori is primarily comprised of grains. People mainly depend upon the food grains they produce or locally available food items and the supply from the public distribution system. This food pattern is changing with the shift in the cropping pattern and the sources of livelihoods. Using an interview schedule, this research is carried out based on the data collected from the field with 250 households of 21 villages covering all seven CD blocks of the district. The primary food sources of tribal people are cereals, pulses, and vegetables, whereas the consumption of meat and milk is significantly less and occasionally. The data illustrated that the per capita food consumption pattern comprises cereals (45.6%) and pulses (22.4%). 66% of members of the sampled households used to take meals twice a day, and the rest, 34%, thrice a day. The food consumption pattern is precisely related to the cropping pattern of the area. 79.2% of households' calorie intake falls below the recommended dietary allowances of ICMR; hence, they are malnourished and underweight.

Keywords Tribes, food consumption pattern, food frequency, calories intake

Introduction

The food consumption pattern is an important indicator of health status. Anthropologists and other social scientists have widely studied it. Prabhat and Begum (2012:321) pointed out that food consumption pattern fundamentally reflects the nutritional well-being of individuals, and the meal pattern is defined by culture and food availability. The views of Murugkar and Pal (2004:268) are relevant to mention here as dietary intake patterns and socioeconomic variables are well-known indicators for assessing the nutritional status of a society.

Objective of study

- To study the food consumption pattern among tribal people
- To analyse the food consumption frequency and calorie intake

Review of Literature Ngoen et al. (2010:335) have examined that several socioeconomic factors, such as family income, influence food purchasing and consumption behaviour affect the consumption pattern of people. The prevailing agricultural practices and proximity to the forests largely influence the food habits of tribal people. According to Joshi and Raghav (2021:14), food habits are highly influenced by society's thoughts, beliefs, notions, traditions, and taboos. Besides these sociocultural barriers, religion, education, and economic factors alter food behaviors (habits). Reddy and Rao (2000:16) have reported that nutrition is one of the most potent environmental factors that influence an individual's optimal health, and it is indirectly influenced by family income, occupation, family size, and other ecological constituents. Chakma et al. (2006:198) have defined nutritional status as the population largely dependent on food consumption, which is influenced by food availability and purchasing power. Some of the important studies on the said field are from Hoar et. al.(1955); Lostroh et. al.(1958); Scow (1959); Sneed et. al. (1961); Nicall et. al. (1965); Belsare et. al. (1966); Yamazaki (1976); Holder et. al. (1980); Miwa et. al. (1985); Tay et. al. (1997); Lakra , et.al. (1996); Wilson ,et al.(1998);

Islam, et. al.(2021); Hasan, et.al. (2021); Romain ,et.al. (2022). Brown et.al.(1995) and that of Nayak et. al. (2000).

Main Text

The tribal population dominates the Dindori district and lies on the undulating terrain of the Mokal hills. Agriculture is the primary source of livelihood for the inhabitants. The agriculture of the area is mainly contingent on rainfall. There is a lack of irrigation facilities and capital inputs. The agricultural practices of the area depict its peculiar traits, from traditional subsistence to modern. The present study focuses on food consumption pattern, food frequency, and calorie intake among tribal people in the district.

The study area

Dindori district lies between latitudes 22° 27' N to 23°23' N and longitudes 80°30' E to 81°44' E. The district's total area is 7,470 sq. km (DCH, 2011:3). The Maikal hill ranges lie east-west in the district, and the area's elevation varies between 300m to 1100m above mean sea level. The study area is drained by the river Narmada and its tributaries. The district received an average rainfall of 1110.72mm from 2001 to 2017. The average maximum and minimum temperatures were recorded as 43.63°C and 2.18°C, respectively, during the same period (DSB, 2019-20).

Dindori district was carved out from the Mandla district on May 25, 1998. The district has 942 villages and is comprised of seven CD blocks, namely Dindori, Shahpura, Mehandwani, Amarpur, Bajag, Karanjija, and Samnapur (shown in fig. 1). According to the 2011 census, the district has 7,04,524 persons. 95.42% of the total population inhabited rural areas, whereas 64.69% of the district's population belongs to tribal communities as part of the Central Indian tribal belt. The high sex ratio (1002 females per thousand males) in the district is due to the tribal population and their egalitarian society. The 87.46% working population of Dindori is cultivators and agricultural labourers.

Fig. 1

Methodology This study is primarily based on field survey data collected from 250 households of 21 villages from all seven blocks of the Dindori district. The systematic sampling technique is used in the selection of villages and households, whereas the sample size was determined based on the formula as follows: . The p-value is 0.293 (29.3/100 = 0.293) derived from the body mass index of women aged 15-49 in Dindori district (29.3% as per the NFHS 2020-21 report). The q value is 0.707 = (1-p i.e., 1-0.293 = 0.707). The percentage-related standard error (PRSE) was 10%, i.e., 0.10 (10/100 = 0.10). The calculation gave an output of 241.293, rounded to 250 sample households. The systematic sampling technique selected 4% of sample villages from the list of villages with a tribal population of more than 76% in each CD block. The 250 households were divided into 21 sample villages, resulting in 11.9 households per village. Based on a systematic sampling method, this number was rounded to 12 households for each selected village. The field survey was conducted with the help of an interview schedule. The schedule consists of both structured and unstructured questions. The 24-hour dietary recall method has been used to delineate per person per day consumption of food items

and their quantity. Questions were asked of the respondents about the types of raw material and the amount of food items used in cooking for breakfast, lunch, and dinner the whole day before the survey. The food consumption unit of the households is grams per person per day, which is calculated from the total quantity (grams) of raw food material used for cooking divided by the total number of family members of the same household. The Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) recommended dietary allowances (RDA) guideline has been used to determine food consumption per person per day. The data is processed with the help of MS Excel and SPSS. The QGIS (38) and ArcGIS 10.8 software versions were employed in the map-making.

Result and Discussion

Food consumption pattern: cereals, pulses, vegetables, milk and meat

Food is an essential element of human life. Good nutritious food provides calories, vitamins, carbohydrates, fat, and protein, while low-quality food cannot help the human body's growth; it is also responsible for mental disorders and nutritional deficiencies. Bhoi and Kumar (2023:1) find out that the nutritional status of tribal groups is inadequate because they do not know about their food and its nutrients. Suryawanshi and Kate (2023:83) stated that an individual's health is primarily determined by nutrition, and it is determined by diet, which consists of a variety of food items. In the 24-hour dietary recall method, the respondents were asked about the food items used in their diets. The household data revealed that the primary source of food and nutrients is cereals, pulses, and vegetables; moreover, meat is consumed occasionally, and milk is not common among the tribal people in this region. Jerath et al. (2016:2265) studied the contribution of indigenous foods towards nutrient intakes and nutritional status of women in the Santhal tribal community of Jharkhand. They stated that although the community is aware of the traditional knowledge regarding the availability and accessibility of these items, it may not make the best use of them due to a lack of information about their nutritional value. Hameed and Vaida (2017:2004) summarized their study's result as poor nutritional status of scheduled tribe women. They were undernourished and had inadequate nutrient intake, showing a high percentage deficit in calories, proteins, iron, and calcium intake.

The ICMR has recommended the consumption of cereals (420 grams), pulses (40 grams), and vegetables (125 grams) per person per day. The primary data revealed that 45.6% of households consume cereals that are lower than the recommended dietary allowances. The consumption pattern of pulses revealed that 77.6% of households consumed above the recommended level of ICMR. In contrast, the consumption of vegetables revealed that 79.2% of households consumed vegetables lower than 125 grams/per person/day. Gupta and Mishra (2014:12) described that the consumption of different food items varies among socio-economic groups and regions. Chakma et al. (2014:1) reported that the consumption of all the foodstuffs except cereals and millets was lower than the recommended dietary allowances, and the intake of micronutrients was also lower than the recommended nutritional allowances among Baiga people of Baihar and Balaghat districts of Madhya Pradesh.

Consumption of cereals

According to DeFries et al. (2018:378), cereals provide a substantial proportion of calories for the human population and cover more than half of the world's cropland area. The ICMR has recommended consuming 420 grams of cereals per person per day for a healthy life. Still, the field data revealed that 45.6% of members of the sampled household consume cereals lower than the recommended level. In contrast, Patange et al. (2018:95) studied the consumption pattern of tribal households in the Palghar district of Maharashtra. They discovered that cereal consumption exceeded the bare requirements. When compared to the recommended dietary allotment, additional food items such as pulses, leafy greens, other vegetables, roots and tubers, fats and oils, milk and milk products, meat foods and eggs, spices, and sugar were lower.

The village-wise cereal consumption pattern has been categorized as above 420 grams and below 420 grams per person per day. Table 1 revealed that the highest percentage of cereals consumption is visible in Dalka Khamariya Ryt (91.67%), while the lowest consumption is in Kamarasondha (18.18%). The village-wise distribution of cereal consumption is divided into three categories: high (more than 65%), medium (45 to 65%), and low (below 45%). The households from eight villages fall under the category of high cereals consumption namely Dalka Khamariya Ryt (91.67%), Bharwae Mal (75%), Bhimkundi (75%), Tikra Khamariya Mal (75%), Dhanauli (66.67%), Kapa (66.67%), Musamundi (66.67%) and Sarwahi Mal (66.67%). This high consumption of cereals pertains to the enormous production of cereals such as paddy, maize, wheat, and kodonkutki in these villages and the availability of suitable soils and weather conditions for producing cereals.

Table 1. Dindori district (MP): Consumption pattern of cereals, pulses, and vegetables at the household level

Sl. No.	Sampled villages	Consumption pattern of cereals				Consumption pattern of pulses				Consumption pattern of vegetables				Total HHs
		Above 420		Below 420		Above 40		Below 40 grams/person/ day		Above 125 grams/person/ day		Below 125 grams/person/ day		
		households	%	households	%	households	%	households	%	households	%	households	%	
1.	Bharvae Mal	9	75.00	3	25.00	10	83.33	2	16.67	4	33.33	8	66.67	12
2.	Bhimkundi	9	75.00	3	25.00	10	83.33	2	16.67	0	0.00	12	100.00	12
3.	Bligson	6	50.00	6	50.00	10	83.33	2	16.67	1	8.33	11	91.67	12
4.	Dadarghughri	7	58.33	5	41.67	9	75.00	3	25.00	4	33.33	8	66.67	12
5.	Dalka	11	91.67	1	8.33	7	58.33	5	41.67	2	16.67	10	83.33	12
6.	Dhanauli	8	66.67	4	33.33	11	91.67	1	8.33	3	25.00	9	75.00	12
7.	Dhurkuta	7	58.33	5	41.67	8	66.67	4	33.33	1	8.33	11	91.67	12
8.	Gopalpur	4	33.33	8	66.67	7	58.33	5	41.67	8	66.67	4	33.33	12
9.	Jagalpur	4	36.36	7	63.64	11	100.00	0	0.00	1	9.09	10	90.91	11
10.	Kamarasondha	2	18.18	9	81.82	9	81.82	2	18.18	1	9.09	10	90.91	11
11.	Kapa	8	66.67	4	33.33	8	66.67	4	33.33	7	58.33	5	41.67	12
12.	Katehra	5	41.67	7	58.33	7	58.33	5	41.67	5	41.67	7	58.33	12
13.	Makke Ryt	6	50.00	6	50.00	10	83.33	2	16.67	1	8.33	11	91.67	12
14.	Tikra	9	75.00	3	25.00	9	75.00	3	25.00	5	41.67	7	58.33	12
15.	Khamariya Mal	8	66.67	4	33.33	12	100.00	0	0.00	1	8.33	11	91.67	12
16.	Musamundi	5	41.67	7	58.33	9	75.00	3	25.00	3	25.00	9	75.00	12
17.	Parapani	4	33.33	8	66.67	10	83.33	2	16.67	2	16.67	10	83.33	12
18.	Patan Mal	7	58.33	5	41.67	8	66.67	4	33.33	1	8.33	11	91.67	12
19.	Ramhepur	3	25.00	9	75.00	7	58.33	5	41.67	0	0.00	12	100.00	12
20.	Roosa	6	50.00	6	50.00	12	100.00	0	0.00	2	16.67	10	83.33	12
21.	Sarvahi Mal	8	66.67	4	33.33	10	83.33	2	16.67	0	0.00	12	100.00	12
Total		136	54.40	114	45.60	194	77.60	56	22.40	52	20.80	198	79.20	250

Source: Primary data collected from field survey, April-June 2022

Fig. 2 (a) Consumption of Cereals, (b) Consumption of Pulses, (c) Consumption of vegetables

Source: Based on primary data collected from field survey, April-June 2022

The households of six villages, namely Dadarghughri (58.33%), Dhurkuta (58.33%), Pathariya Ryt (58.33%), Bilgaon (50%), Makke Ryt (50%), and Roosa (50%) come under medium consumption of cereals whereas, rest seven villages Katehra (41.67%), Parapani (41.67%), Jagatpur (36.36%), Gopalpur (33.33%), Patan Mal (33.33%), Ramhepur (25%) and Kamarasondha (18.18%) belongs to low consumption of cereals. The causes of low consumption of cereals are associated with the low production of cereals in these villages.

Consumption of pulses

In developing countries, the consumption of pulses is most common in their diet. Indian food system consists of pulses, which are the primary source of protein; therefore, farmers produce enough pulses. The primary data analysis unveiled that most households consume pigeon peas and lentil pulses, followed by gram, peas, and black gram seasonally. The consumption pattern of pulses has been classed as above 40 grams and below 40 grams per person per day based on the recommended dietary allowance guideline by ICMR. Table 1 illustrates that 77.6% of households consumed pulses more than 40 grams per person per day, whereas 22.4% of households were below the recommended level. The highest percentage of pulse consumption is visible in three villages, Musamundi, Jagatpur, and Roosa, where all households consume more than 40 grams of pulses per person daily. The four villages, Dalka Khamariya Ryt, Gopalpur, Katehra, and Ramhepur, show a contrasting scenario where many households consume pulses lower than the recommended level. The village-wise distribution of pulse consumption among the tribal households is mainly categorized as high (more than 75%), medium (60% to 75%), and low (below 60%). The households from the eleven villages belong to the high consumption category, these villages are Jagatpur (100%), Musamundi (100%), Roosa (100%), Dhanauli (91.67%), Bharwae Mal (83.33%), Bhimkundi (83.33%), Bilgaon (83.33%), Makke Ryt (83.33%), Patan Mal (83.33%), Sarwahi Mal (83.33%) and Kamarasondha (81.82%). This high consumption of pulses is associated with the better production of lentils, pigeon peas, peas, and grams in the area. Six villages namely Dadarghughri (75%), Tikra Khamariya Mal (75%), Parapani (75%), Dhurkuta (66.67%), Kapa (66.67%) and Pathariya Ryt (66.67%) come under the medium category and rest four villages namely Dalka Khamariya Ryt (58.33%), Gopalpur (58.33%), Katehra (58.33%) and Ramhepur (58.33%) show more than 50% of households consume pulses below the recommended level.

Consumption of vegetables

Vegetables are an essential source of minerals broadly used in the Indian food system. Tribal people of the study area use many types of stems, leaves, fruits, seeds, roots, and tubers as vegetables supported by various mushrooms available in the rainy season. The primary data show that the consumption pattern of vegetables was low in the study area. The ICMR has recommended vegetable consumption of 125 grams per person per day. Table 1 shows that 79.2% of households consume less than 125 grams per person per day, and the rest, 20.8%, consume vegetables at the recommended level. Rao et al. (2015:690) have also found the low consumption of leafy vegetables in the diet and nutrition profile of the Chenchu tribe in Telangana and Andhra Pradesh, India.

The village-wise distribution of vegetable consumption is categorized into high (more than 40%), medium (20 to 40%), and low (below 20%). Table 1 revealed that high consumption of vegetables among the households is visible in four villages, namely Gopalpur (66.67%), Kapa (58.33%), Katehra (41.67%), and Tikra Khamariya Mal (41.67%), where more than 40% of households consume vegetables at the recommended level. In contrast, families from the villages Bharwae Mal (33.33%), Dadarghughari (33.33%), Dhanuali (25%), and Parapani (25%) come under the medium category in the context of vegetable consumption. Thirteen villages out of twenty-one villages belong to the category of low vegetable consumption namely Dalka Khamariya Ryt (16.67%), Patan Mal (16.67%), Roosa (16.67%), Jagatpur (9.09%), Kamarasondha (9.09%), Bilgaon (8.33%), Dhurkuta (8.33%), Makke Ryt (8.33%), Musamundi (8.33%), Pathariya Ryt (8.33%) and rest three villages namely Bhimkundi, Ramhepur and Sarwahi Mal have reported 100% of the households consume vegetables below the recommended level (<125 grams per person per day). Low preference for vegetables in their diet results from less vegetable production and people's low purchasing power. The preference for peji (millet-based gruel) and bhaji (leafy vegetables), a light dish, also affected their food system, especially vegetable consumption.

Consumption of milk and meat

Meat and milk are the sources of protein, minerals, and fats for healthy and active life. In the Dindori district, the tribal people used less meat in their diet because of its poor availability and lack of purchasing power, whereas milk consumption is not in their dietary practice; hence, milk is used rarely. Similar findings were reported in the study by Mittal and Srivastava (2006:1), Every Oraon group's diet lacked certain food groups. Cereal consumption was the least inadequate, whereas fruit and milk intake was nonexistent. Dheki saag, a locally cultivated green leafy vegetable, and fermented leftover rice were added to their diet. Jaiswal (2013:16) has also found that the low value of carotene and riboflavin could be due to the low intake of green vegetables and a negligible amount of milk in the diet of the Bhumia tribe of Madhya Pradesh.

The responses of the people revealed that most of the households of the sampled villages rarely used milk in their diet except for the condition of being sick or infected with any disease. At the same time, meat consumption is frequent on all social and cultural occasions. Qamra et al. (2006:211) studied the food consumption pattern of the Bhil tribe and found that milk, milk products, and sugar are almost absent from their daily diet.

Milk consumption is greatly affected by the purchasing power of the household or the availability of milch cattle. Most families have bulls only for agricultural activities. The ICMR has recommended milk consumption of 150 grams per person per day, while meat is recommended 25 grams per person per day in dietary intake. No person was found to have meat in the last twenty-four hours during the field study, even though most tribal households belong to non-vegetarian groups. This means that the consumption of both milk and meat is below the recommended dietary allowance.

Fig. 3
Source: Based on Table 1

Food Frequency

Food frequency is one of the most critical factors that affects the quantity of food intake and the consumption pattern. The food quantity is high when they consume food thrice a

day as breakfast, lunch, and dinner, rather than twice a day. Respondents were asked how many times they ate the food in a day. The primary field data revealed that 66% of households consume meals twice daily, and the remaining 34% reported thrice daily. Thus, food frequency affects the food consumption pattern and calorie intake among tribal people.

The village-wise food intake is categorised into high (more than 75% HHs), medium (50 to 75%), and low (less than 50%). Table 2 depicts that the highest percentage of twice food intake is visible in eight villages, namely Katehra (100%), Parapani (100%), Gopalpur (91.67%), Kamarasondha (90.91%), Roosa (83.33%), Ramhepur (76.92%), Bharwae Mal and Patan Mal (75%). All these villages have a higher percentage medium size of family (two to five members), primarily engaged in agriculture activities. The lowest twice food intake is visible in four villages, namely Bilgaon (46.15%), Makke Ryt (41.67%), Tikra Khamariya Mal (41.67%), and Bhimkundi (33.33%). The households of the remaining twelve villages come under the medium category of twice food intake.

Only 34% of households in the district reported taking meals three times a day. A higher proportion of households having food intake thrice a day was reported in Bhimkundi (66.67%), Makke Ryt (58.33%), Tikra Khamariya Mal (58.33%), and Bilgaon (53.85%) villages. It was observed from the collected data that those households have children, and they have meals thrice a day. In contrast, wherever fewer members are in the families, or all the members are adults and mature, they consume food twice daily. Respondents also stated that the number of meals and quantity of their food increased or decreased according to weather conditions and the seasons.

Table 2. Dindori district (MP): Frequency of food consumption and calorie intake among the selected households

Sl. No.	Sampled villages	Food frequency				Calorie intake				Total HHs
		Twice a day		Thrice a day		Less than 2400 kcal (per person/day)		2400 kcal and Above (per person/day)		
		households	%	households	%	households	%	households	%	
1.	Bharwae Mal	9	75.00	3	25.00	8	66.67	4	33.33	12
2.	Bhimkundi	4	33.33	8	66.67	9	75.00	3	25.00	12
3.	Bilgaon	6	46.15	7	53.85	11	91.67	1	8.33	12
4.	Dadarghughri	8	66.67	4	33.33	12	100.00	0	0.00	12
5.	Daika Khamariya Ryt	6	50.00	6	50.00	9	75.00	3	25.00	12
6.	Dhanauli	8	66.67	4	33.33	10	83.33	2	16.67	12
7.	Dhurkuta	7	58.33	5	41.67	11	91.67	1	8.33	12
8.	Gopalpur	11	91.67	1	8.33	10	83.33	2	16.67	12
9.	Jagatpur	5	55.56	4	44.44	8	72.73	3	27.27	12
10.	Kamarasondha	10	90.91	1	9.09	11	100.00	0	0.00	12
11.	Kapa	8	66.67	4	33.33	8	66.67	4	33.33	12
12.	Katehra	12	100.00	0	0.00	10	83.33	2	16.67	12
13.	Makke Ryt	5	41.67	7	58.33	10	83.33	2	16.67	12
14.	Tikra Khamariya Mal	5	41.67	7	58.33	10	83.33	2	16.67	12
15.	Musamundi	6	50.00	6	50.00	11	91.67	1	8.33	12
16.	Parapani	12	100.00	0	0.00	10	83.33	2	16.67	12
17.	Patan Mal	9	75.00	3	25.00	8	66.67	4	33.33	12
18.	Pathariya Ryt	7	58.33	5	41.67	10	83.33	2	16.67	12
19.	Ramhepur	10	76.92	3	23.08	12	100.00	0	0.00	12
20.	Roosa	10	83.33	2	16.67	11	91.67	1	8.33	12
21.	Sarwahi Mal	7	58.33	5	41.67	6	50.00	6	50.00	12
	Total	165	66.00	85	34.00	205	82.00	45	18.00	250

Source: Primary Data Collected from Field Survey, April-June 2022

Calorie Intake

A society's nutritional status can be determined using well-known markers such as socioeconomic factors and dietary intake patterns. Food is essential for the development and active life because it is the source of carbohydrates, fats, proteins, vitamins, and minerals. Calorie is a part of food that helps the growth of the human body. Table 2 represents the calorie intake of the tribal community at the household level in the sampled village of the Dindori district. This data illustrated that 82% of households intake calories below 2400 kcal per person per day, and the remaining households (18%) intake more than 2400 kcal per person per day in the study area. This means more than eighty percent of households intake calories less than the recommended level of ICMR (2400 kcal per person per day) and are malnourished. Patange et al. (2018:95) found that tribal people of the Palghar district of Maharashtra intake calories (2263 kcal) below the recommended level. Similarly, Jerath et al. (2022) studied Indigenous food intake and nutritional status of Munda women and found that these women are eating low calories in winter and monsoon seasons. Bisai et al. (2023) have also found low-calorie intake (2290 kcal per capita) among Oraon people in West Bengal.

The village-wise analysis of calorie intake revealed that the highest percentage of calorie intake among tribal people is visible in Sarwahi Mal village, where half of the households' intake calories more than 2400 kcal whereas, in the households of the remaining twenty villages, the intake of calories is below the recommended level. 100% of households in the villages of Dadarghughri, Kamrasondha, and Ramhepur intake calories below the recommended level, while 35% of 17 villages intake calories below the recommended level. The low-calorie intake is directly related to the food system, which contains low calories such as pej and bhaji and dried leafy and other vegetables. Likewise, Reddy and Rao (2000:16) studied the dietary habits, food consumption, and nutrient intake of Sugali

tribes in Andhra Pradesh. They reported suffering from a calorie gap rather than a protein gap. Further, it was stated that providing protein concentrates will not prevent protein-calorie malnutrition without correcting the existing calorie gap.

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

Source: Based on Primary Data Collected from Field Survey, April-June 2022

Conclusion

The study of food consumption patterns among the surveyed households revealed that 54.4% consume cereals above the recommended level of ICMR (420 grams per person per day), whereas 45.6% consume them below the recommended level. The highest consumption of cereals is visible in Dalka Khamariya Ryt village (91.67%), while village Kamarasondha (18.18%) shows the lowest consumption of cereals. The consumption pattern of pulses shows that 77.6% of households consume pulses more than the recommended level (40 grams/person/day), while 22.4% of households consume it below the recommended level. This data clearly shows that pulse consumption is high in the district, which is interlinked with the better production of pulses. The soil characteristics and weather conditions are suitable for the cultivation of pulse crops in the district, and that is why most households produce pulse crops: lentils, pigeon peas, peas, and gram. The consumption pattern of vegetables in the study area was low; 79.2% of households consumed vegetables below the recommended level (125 grams/person/day), while only 20.8% consumed more than the recommended dietary allowances. People largely depend on green vegetables grown in baris or collected from forests with limited and seasonal availability. Some households also reported that poor economic conditions also affect the low consumption of vegetables. This overall scenario of the consumption pattern revealed a high pulse consumption in the district. In contrast, the consumption of cereals and vegetables is less than the recommended level. It shows that the food consumption among tribal people is below the ICMR guidelines; consequently, their health status is poor.

Two-thirds of households from the sampled villages consume meals twice daily, and one-third take food thrice daily. This is associated with the number of family members and families having children. Furthermore, weather conditions and seasons also affect the quantity and number of daily meals. 82% of households intake calories below 2400 kcal per person daily, and only 18% intake calories above the recommended level. This implies that more than eighty percent of people are malnourished and underweight

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